
Influence of Digital Marketing Dimensions on Online Purchase Intentions and Customer Satisfaction: An Analytical Study**Sana Ashraf¹****DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20073122>****Review: 01/01/2026****Acceptance: 04/01/2026****Publication: 25/04/2026**

Abstract: *One of the best educational approaches is value education. However, due to a number of factors, this system is only applicable in developed nations. The goal of this research is to create a training programme for primary school teachers who will be able to implement value education programmes in underdeveloped nations. Teachers hold values in addition to imparting knowledge of the principles of science and assisting in the development of particular skills and practises in a particular field. In primary schools, where the foundations of worldview are formed, this is crucial. But in the modern era, numerous factors are to blame for the deterioration of teachers' status, their subpar performance, and the loss of teaching values.*

Keywords: *Primary Level, Teachers, Training Programs, Values, Academic Motivation, Education System.*

Introduction:

Instead of developing their educational values, teachers at the primary level are actively participating in political topics. If the researchers study the job satisfaction of the teacher, then they find that the satisfaction of the post, the satisfaction of salary is definitely reflected in comparison to their work, while education policies, education principles, and methods of education are made for the best development of the inherent powers in the child. But the teachers are making their teaching so monotonous that the student remains mentally absent in the class. As a result, the learning level of the students is getting degraded and creativity of the students is dying out. Another terrible result of this is that the student learns to pass the exam by rote since childhood. For economic development, some teachers also reach the parents' place to teach tuition and coaching to the children, but the collective development of the children gets blocked, due to which the child suffering from frustration becomes a small adult.

Teaching is a performing activity that provides an opportunity for students to learn. The purpose of the teacher is to teach the students and achieve their educational goals. They play a different roles when they deal with students. Sometimes they are a friend, sometimes they are in the role of a coach, guide and director. Therefore teaching can be expressed as decision making, direction, guidance and instruction. In order to understand the teacher's values towards teaching from the right perspective, it seems appropriate to study some definitions of teaching.

Ahluwalia (1971) emphasized that the study of teachers' values is very important. He observed that how a teacher performs his/her duty as a teacher depends largely on his/her values and beliefs. A teacher's attitude affects not only his behaviour in the classroom but also the behaviour of his students. A positive friendly attitude not only makes the job easier but also a more satisfying and rewarding profession.

1. Values of primary teachers towards students

The teacher's attitude towards students is also important in determining the classroom climate. The learning environment is subjective and we all adopt children's methods to determine whether a teacher likes children. Both

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teachers and pupils have different personal values. Some instructors think that children need to be pushed to work hard because they are inherently lazy and lack discipline. They develop a conservative and dictatorial approach toward their pupils as a consequence of this viewpoint. Conservative authoritarian educators uphold the status quo of the classroom teacher's position of power. Students must always uphold this right. Students that act inappropriately are disciplined in order to instil moral values. In the classroom, strict discipline is maintained by regularly administering incentives and penalties. The promotion of pupils' personal liberty is not given much attention. Instead, they are expected to put forth a lot of effort to meet the objectives that their instructor has set.

Other educators, on the other hand, think that each student has a distinct personality and is capable of practising self-direction and self-control when focused on learning goals. This conviction leads him to instil liberal and democratic ideas in his pupils. Every pupil has inherent potential that can be developed, according to liberal-democratic educators. He puts a lot of effort into helping his pupils tap into their inner potential. Teachers that practise liberal democracy treat their pupils with respect and courtesy and encourage them to choose their own objectives. Instead of reprimanding or penalising the pupils, they deal with disobedient students using ethical and rational strategies.

2. Contemporary Issues of Primary School Teacher Training

The fact that kids are overwhelmed by the very diversified material of another subject is one of the current concerns with prospective elementary school instructors' study programmes. On the other hand, they lack any subject-matter expertise. It is said that educators are specialists and professionals in instructing young children and that they aid in the development of the skills and aptitudes that serve as the cornerstones of lifetime learning. Another problem is that not all primary school trainee teachers go on to get full teaching certifications. The majority of them lack the credentials necessary to instruct in a foreign language in a primary setting. This certification is only available to people who successfully complete a specific degree in teaching foreign languages to elementary school kids. Only 30% of all aspiring elementary school teachers get this certification. The fact that gaining your primary school teaching certification via lifelong learning is almost unattainable at the moment might be considered a significant problem. Only graduates from certain preschool pedagogy or lower secondary school teaching training programmes are eligible for the primary school extension programme.

3. Theoretical Framework on Academic Motivation

Academic motivation is complex. The Academy's motivation is to demand multivariate values for measurement based on multiple theories as well as reliance on multiple validation criteria. A conceptual framework is provided as a background for transforming motivational principles into measures. Three new self-report tools for assessing academic motivation are introduced, namely interest theory, attribution theory and a variant of the expectancy-value theory.

Motivation refers to the factors that influence behaviour, which is characteristic of desire. Extrinsic motivation is controlled by reinforcement contingencies, whereas intrinsic motivation is driven by personal interest or pleasure. A group of closely related beliefs, presumptions, values, lists, and behaviours make up motivation. Individual motivation varies depending on the subject matter, and this domain trait tends to get better with age. Children's motivation predicts motivation later in life, and as they get older, this relationship becomes more stable. In the past, teachers have not believed that intrinsic motivation is preferable to extrinsic motivation and produces better

learning outcomes. In general, it seems that students begin school with an innate desire to pursue higher education. However, as children progress through school, motivation wanes. Teachers should create a supportive classroom environment concerning target structures, qualities and external assessment. There are many challenges in assessing motivation.

4. Literature Review

A research on teacher atmosphere, psychosocial temperament, and academic accomplishment was undertaken by Clifton et al. in 2004. The findings imply that students' perceptions of academic control and coping mechanisms were impacted by both cognitive demands and social support. Academic success of students was thus impacted by the academic atmosphere and psychological disposition.

In 1994, Michael K. Zushiag and Susan Krans Whiteborn conducted a research on the psychosocial growth of college students across three generations. According to the findings, college seniors often develop more than their younger colleagues. Additionally, ladies scored usually higher than boys in terms of psychological development. The absence of cohort differences in the observed patterns of development and the little amount of cohort variations in college courses show that societal forces that have changed through decades of social change have little impact on an individual's development during college.

A research on the institutional influences on the psychological growth of African American college students was undertaken by Chetham et al. in 1990. The research looked into the widely publicised issue and found that historically Black collegiate institutions have been better at fostering the social and intellectual growth of African American college students than historically dominating White collegiate institutions. According to the theory, students from Black college institutions should be better developed than their counterparts at White collegiate institutions if the claimed environmental effects are true. The findings did not clearly support the development of African American college students as a goal of Black collegiate institutions of education. The findings and their implications for further study and consultation were explored. Villar Angueto and Luis Miguel (1987) studied the psychosocial evaluation of the classroom environment. It was concluded that the validity of the instruments was tested concerning reliability, discriminant validity and the ability to differentiate between classes among students. These results can be used to improve teacher training.

Pearl Herald (1986) did a study on the prediction and perception of the psychosocial environment by students. The study examined early expectations and subsequent perceptions of the social climate of university living units as reported by newly entering students and found that freshmen have inaccurate expectations of the future social climate of their living group. The results found differences between students with active and passive social exploration preferences. Jayanti, T. (2004) conducted a study on the influence of social work and receptive learning skills in teacher training.

The findings indicated that personal characteristics i.e. age, gender, teacher, and training did not affect the learning skills. Institutional environment, faculty environment, academic environment, religion, culture, socioeconomic status, learning style, anxiety, and teacher training influenced receptive learning skills. The failure of the personality trait of self-concept tolerance did not affect this. Sinha, R.K. and Bhargav Rajni (1993) have attempted to reveal the effect of deprivation on students' perception of the socio-emotional climate in educational institutions.

The findings are as follows: with respect to the relationship between the perception of the socio-emotional climate and the different components of psychological deprivation, it was found that in most cases no significant effect was obtained for all types of schools. Gupta, Arun, K. and Srinivasan, Nalini (1990) did a study on the fascinating social and educational profile of women teacher training. The results of the study are as follows: As far as women candidates are concerned, there was a marked change in the values towards the teaching profession and the quality of the environment in the BTC course. The reasons presented for joining the BTC course showed that teaching as a discipline was highly valued by the female BTC trainees. Observation of the self-image inventory revealed that the potential average female teacher was likely to be hardworking, disciplined, obedient, conscientious and restrained.

An investigation of the difficulty of creating a college atmosphere in India was done in 1989 by R.C. Srivastava. It has been explored how to govern and lead the environments of Indian colleges and Universities. The necessity to have a professional, open connection with teachers is highlighted while referencing various administrative methods. The need for specialised training to develop leadership qualities in educational institution assistant principals is made.

The organisational environment for school exposure had a beneficial impact on both teaching ability and effectiveness, according to Prakashan's (1988) research on teacher effectiveness as a consequence of classroom management. In terms of both teaching skills and effectiveness, instructors from urban schools greatly outperformed those working in semi-urban, rural, or industrial schools. Regardless of the kind of school or city, women always performed better.

5. Study Objectives: To study the values of primary-level teachers and their impact on students learning.

6. Research Methodology

The descriptive study refers to individual group events and studies such as trend surveys and situations right now to suggest gathering facts and evidence related to the present conditions. A descriptive study is oriented to find out what is required. This study involves a survey method of research. The survey method is an important method that has evolved greatly since the middle of the century and is valuable for many purposes.

The survey becomes the basis of the detection provides detailed information about some of the current cases and describes the main features that are discovered in the study. The present study deals with the psychosocial study of primary-level teachers and teachers' attitudes towards students. The investigator adopted the survey method because it was found suitable for collecting necessary and relevant data.

7.1 Research Design

The present study measures the impact of social work and professional commitment among teachers working in primary schools. Since the survey is the most widely used technique for data collection, this research has been done on the basis of a questionnaire using a standard survey method. The research design will provide a planning structure and strategy for the presented dissertation and will be helpful in case-control so that answers to the research questions can be obtained purely. It has two forms:

- Research Methodology and Methodology Technique will be studied in Structural Structural
- Under operational research tools and statistical methods are used.

7.2 Sampling

The sample consisted of teachers working in primary schools of college of district Hyderabad. This includes both male and female teachers. In the study, 100 teachers were selected. A random sampling technique has been used in this study.

7.3 Instruments Used

The present research has used four instruments along with personal and school-related data sheets to collect the required data for this study. The purpose of personal and school-related data is to collect school teachers' gender teacher grade religion school type management type community teaching experience and monthly income. The details of the equipment are given below.

7.4 Research Instrument

7.4.1 Personal Values Questionnaire- G.P. Sherry and Aarti Verma- The scoring strategy was formulated keeping in view the requirements laid down in the objectives of the study. Scoring of the Personal Values Questionnaire, Vocational Aspiration Scale and Personal Data Sheet has been done as per the instructions given in the respective manuals. In scoring the personal values questionnaire.

7.4.2 The Personal Values Questionnaire developed by Sherry & Verma (1988) was used which has 40 items in 10 subdomains viz. Religious, Social, Democratic, Beauty, Economic, Knowledge, Hedonistic, Credibility, Power, Family Prestige and Health Values and Credibility Coefficient .64, .47, 48, 56, 70, 50, 63, 60, 67 and .52. This instrument has been used by many researchers and has been standardized.

7.5 Statistical Methods: In this study, we are using the following statistical tools: **Average, Standard deviation & T-value**

8. Analysis**8.1 What kind of neighbourhood would you like to live in:**

Well settled and beautiful to look at	43	43%
where you have family neighbors like you	27	27%
where you can lead people	30	30%
Total	100	100%

The above table shows that according to 43% of the respondents, which is well settled and looks beautiful full stop, according to 27% of the respondents, where I am the neighbour of the family like you, and according to 30% of the respondents, where you are the leader of the people. They would love to live in such a locality if possible.

8.2 Who do you consider a good administrator

One who has sympathy and compassion	33	33%
One who maintains strict discipline	35	35%
One who knows the principles of administration	32	32%
Total	100	100%

It can be seen from the above table that 33% of respondents have sympathy and kindness, according to 35% of respondents who keep strict discipline and 32% of respondents who have knowledge of principles of administration, also have good administrators agree.

8.3 On winning one lakh rupees prize in the lottery, three people spent most of it in the following way, who do you think made the best use of the money?

To buy things of your convenience	23	23%
Investing in capital to increase your income	47	47%
To improve your caste	30	30%
Total	100	100%

It can be seen from the above table that 23% of the respondents used to buy their comfort items, 47% of the respondents used to increase their income in the form of capital and 30% of the respondents used their caste. Money has been put to good use for progress.

Table 1: There is no significant difference between the value of specific BTC and general BTC teachers at the primary level.

	N	SD	T-Value	Significance Level
Distinguished BTC Teacher	50	21.5	0.118	0.05
Trained Specialized BTC Teachers	50	14.9		Not Significant

For df=58 at 0.05 level the table t-value is 2.00 at the significance level and the hypothetical value is 0.118. The hypothesis value of 0.118 is less hence hypothesis is rejected. Hence it is inferred that no significant difference is found in the mean scores of typical and similar BTC teachers.

Table 2: Values of general BTC teachers and trained specific BTC teacher

	N	SD	T-Value	Significance Level
General BTC Teacher	50	19.5	5.09	0.05
Trained Specialized BTC Teachers	50	15.9		Not Significant

The above table is based on the values of teachers based on the percentage of BTC and the number of typical BTC male and female teachers is 14.87. The standard deviation of those from 19.5 is 15.9.

9. Conclusion

Only an ideal teacher whose life is a beacon of values can lead society in the right direction. He must demonstrate essential values such as optimism, motivation, a willingness to learn and teach, truthfulness, non-violence, the ability to never speak or think ill of others, creativity, and the ability to demonstrate selfless love. The promotion of human values in society depends on the propagation of good qualities in individuals. In every tradition and every country, not only in the institution but also in the society, the place of the teacher has been made over time. Teachers teaching value education must first acquire and master the knowledge of moral and value education. If they are somehow behind this standard then how can we expect proper teaching of value education?

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